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Original Research Article

Urbanization shapes bird communities and nest survival, but not their food quantity

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ABSTRACT

As urbanization accelerates, there is an increasing focus on understanding the ecological aspects of urbanization (both direct and indirect impacts on communities and biodiversity), monitoring qualitative and quantitative changes in the fauna of urbanized areas, and examining the underlying causes of these changes. To explore the effect of urban areas on avian communities, we examined differences in species richness and abundance of birds, and survival probabilities of artificial shrub nests along an urbanization gradient (rural – suburban – urban) in a medium-sized city in Hungary. Additionally, potential food sources (arthropods captured by sticky traps) and consumption rates by insectivorous birds (predation on dummy caterpillars) were compared along the gradient. Based on our observations, the diversity of species that form bird communities did not change significantly along the gradient. However, significantly more individuals were observed in urban areas than in suburban or rural ones, primarily due to the dominance of synanthropic species: the Domestic (*Columba livia f. domestica*) and Wood Pigeon (*Columba palumbus*), House Sparrow (*Passer domesticus*) and European Blackbird (*Turdus merula*). The daily survival rates of shrub nests were significantly higher in urban and suburban areas than in rural ones. Even so, we did not find any correlations between the species richness of shrub-nesters and urbanization, whilst, they were present with higher abundance in urban than rural habitats. Although the abundance of arthropods as potential food source was not related to the degree of urbanization, the caterpillar predation by birds was significantly higher in suburban than in urban areas. Nevertheless, there were no significant differences in richness of insectivores across urbanization gradients, but their abundance was significantly higher in urban and suburban habitats than in rural ones. In conclusion, no consistent negative or positive urbanization effect could be detected in the present study, but high-level urbanization seems to increase bird abundance. Our results also suggest that shrub-nesting in urban habitats may be safer, probably due to lower predation pressure and/or favourable nesting sites for shrub nesters in cities. Nevertheless, the food availability per se seemed to be not a key driver in habitat selection of birds along the studied urbanization gradient.

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1. Introduction

Urbanization is one of the most extreme forms of environmental alteration, posing a major threat to biodiversity and altering ecosystem services upon which human civilisation depends (Aronson et al., 2014; Sol et al., 2014). The problems caused by urbanization are diverse, though one of the most important is the rapid reduction and transformation of natural habitats of many plants and animal species (e.g. Ramalho and Hobbs, 2012; Seress and Liker, 2015; Johnson and Munshi-South, 2017; Liker, 2020). Cities often create novel ecosystems, characterised by fragmented patches with a higher level of disturbance than natural habitats and with a strongly altered pattern of resources (Rebele, 1994), but can provide new opportunities as well. Birds respond to urban ecosystems by either avoiding cities or by adapting and even exploiting the urban landscape. Besides the negative impacts as disturbance and noise or light pollution that cause changes to physiological traits (Partecke et al., 2006), there are some benefits too. Cities function as heat islands, thereby provide warmer habitats also in winter, rich sources of food (including wastes and bird-feeders), and often safety from predators that are deterred by humans or domestic pets, and from parasites (Eötvös et al., 2018; Møller, 2012; Geue and Partecke, 2008). In general, urbanization is thought to depress biodiversity for many taxa, and humanity's causative role in this process is potentially straightforward (McIntyre et al., 2000; Marzluff, 2001). However, the relationship between humans and wildlife in urban areas is complex, since different taxa respond differently to the ecological consequences of urbanization (McKinney, 2008; Parris, 2016; Ouyang et al., 2018).

As the persistence of biodiversity in urban areas, as well as the green environment in cities, are important for the well-being of human residents (Turner et al., 2004), the restoration of biodiversity becomes more emphasized in urban planning (Taylor et al., 2013). For such efforts, it is increasingly important to understand the relationship between wildlife and urban habitats (Clergeau et al., 1998). Since birds are often used as biodiversity indicators and have frequent interactions with humans (Evans et al., 2009), their abundance and community composition in urban areas have been well studied (Gil and Brumm, 2014; Kelcey and Rheinwald, 2005; Marzluff, 2001) with the main conclusion that urban development leads to the dominance of few abundant species, and long-term homogenization of diversity (Chace and Walsh, 2006; Morelli et al., 2016). Several studies compared demographic parameters of bird populations (such as the timing of nesting, clutch size, fledging rate, annual survival) between urban and semi-natural populations (e.g. Chace and Walsh, 2006; Kosinski, 2001). However, the few attempts to assess a general effect of urbanization on avian demography (e.g. Jerzak, 1995; Marzluff, 2001; Seress et al., 2020) have not been comprehensive (Chamberlain et al., 2009). Several factors such as food resources, the availability of suitable nest sites, interspecific competition and predation are important in determining avian habitat selection and community structure (Jokimäki and Huhta, 2000). Nest predation, in particular, is assumed to influence avian population density, reproductive ecology and life history, but there are few empirical studies on how the nest predation pressure affects the structure of bird communities (Jokimäki and Huhta, 2000; Jokimäki et al., 2020; Shochat et al., 2006; Stracey and Robinson, 2012). Nest predation pressure may vary both between and within habitats (i.e. between microhabitats) due to differences in predator communities and densities, vegetation structure and complexity, and the intensity of human activities (Eötvös et al., 2018; Loiselle and Farji-Brener, 2002). Furthermore, changes in vegetation cover alter the arthropod communities as well as their availability for birds. Therefore, food accessibility can play a primary role in shaping the demographic parameters of bird populations and thereby their community structure (Seress et al., 2018).

The process of urbanization shows significant variation across and within countries. There is no general agreement in a definition of what is urban, and considerable differences in classification of urban and rural habitats exist among countries and continents (Francis and Chadwick, 2013; McIntyre et al., 2000; Seto et al., 2013), thus not only the characteristics of individual cities may affect responses along the rural-urban gradient, but also category definitions may differ from study to study (Batáry et al., 2018). In Europe, the urban landscape is often defined as an area with >50% of the surface built, surrounded by 30–50% built-up areas, and a population density: >1000 persons/km² (Elmqvist et al., 2008). Population size, the density of economic activity or the form of governance structure are also used to delineate what is a city region, but there is significant variation in the criteria for defining what is urban (Seto et al., 2013). Another problem is that different kinds of habitat patches are often scattered within cities, including gardens, green areas between houses, semi-natural parks, housing complexes, densely built-up areas or industrial areas, resulting in heterogeneity at different spatial scales, which can play a role in birds' life in different ways (Tryjanowski et al., 2017). Thus, behavioural responses of animals to urban gradients may differ in part due to variations in gradient composition.

To maintain the biodiversity in urban habitats, more accurate knowledge about factors determining the distribution of species and the structure of the communities is required. Therefore, it is important to take a holistic view, and describe not only the composition of bird communities but monitoring the breeding success and the factors affecting them. Here, we studied bird communities, nest predation and food resources at the same time and same study system. For this reason, we examined (1) the differences in bird community compositions across different habitats with varied levels of urbanization (urban-suburban-rural gradient) in a mid-sized European city. Furthermore, we investigated (2) whether nest survival probabilities of shrub nester birds and (3) potential food sources for insectivorous birds differ along this urbanization gradient.

For this purpose, we applied basic bird census techniques and exposed artificial nests to measure the relative levels of nest predation. The latter method is frequently used by bird ecologists and ornithologists to compare nest predation rates among species or habitats in order to avoid their disturbance and overcome logistical problems (Jokimäki and Huhta, 2000; Jokimäki et al., 2005; Moore and Robinson, 2004). Although this method has received criticism due to limited transferability of results

to natural nests (Faaborg, 2004), many authors have shown this method to be adequate tools for spatial comparison of nest predation (e.g. Batáry and Báldi, 2005; Kurucz et al., 2012), and may provide an additional source of data to natural nests when testing ecological hypotheses.

To compare available food between these habitats, the abundance of arthropods was assessed by yellow sticky traps, that are one of the simplest and time-efficient ways to monitor abundances of flying insects (Heinz et al., 1992; McCravy, 2018). Additionally, differences in the relative intensity of insectivory upon herbivorous larvae were experimentally assessed as the frequency of birds' attacks upon insect larvae, since caterpillars are one of the most important food resources for many songbirds (Holmes et al., 1979). For this purpose, dummy caterpillars were used as sentinel prey, since this technique has been successfully applied in multiple studies to quantify predation pressure in testing a multitude of hypotheses (e.g. Barber, 2012; Howe et al., 2009; Lövei and Ferrante, 2017; Roslin et al., 2017). Just like in case of artificial nests, these models do not provide an estimation of natural predation rates, but traces left by different predators are identifiable, making it suitable for comparative studies and useable as a means to obtain standardized estimates of predation rates (Gunnarsson et al., 2018; Loiselle and Farji-Brener, 2002). In summary, we expected a decrease in bird richness and food availability, but increasing bird abundance, caterpillar predation and nest predation along the urbanization gradient.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area and habitat description

The study was conducted in Pécs, the largest city of the South-Transdanubian region (Baranya county) in Hungary, bordered by the Mecsek mountains from the north, and a plain from the south (46°04'21.84" N, 18°13'56.16" E). The town has 142 873 inhabitants and covering an area of 162.8 km² (HCSO, 2019). Sub-Mediterranean climate with four seasons characterises the Mecsek Mountains, summer is warm with occasional fast showers and winter is mild but rather humid, and hence the town with a mean annual precipitation of 710 mm and a mean annual temperature of 10 °C.

We defined three different habitat types along the urbanization gradient, as follows like in most urban ecological studies: (1) *rural habitats* as a transition between the populated area and natural or agricultural environment; (2) *suburban habitats* as moderately urbanized environments; and (3) *urban habitats* as highly urbanized environments. For this definition, we used the European Urban Atlas (EUA, 2018), which provides reliable, inter-comparable, high-resolution land use maps for cities of EU member states with more than 100 000 inhabitants. Applying this database enables to use the same classification of urbanization levels for other studies in European cities involved in EUA dataset, making data potentially comparable (EUA, 2018). We clustered the following land-use type categories (nomenclature and vector data codes) used by the EUA representing the three different habitat types: Urban habitats: „Continuous urban fabric (Average degree of soil sealing layer (S.L.) > 80%) – 11100" and „Industrial, commercial, public, military and private units – 12100" together; Suburban habitats: „Discontinuous dense urban fabric (S.L.: 50%–80%) – 11210", „Discontinuous medium density urban fabric (S.L.: 30%–50%) – 11220", „Green urban areas – 14100" and „Sports and leisure facilities – 14200" together; Rural habitats: „Discontinuous low-density urban fabric (S.L.: 10%–30%) – 11230", „Discontinuous very-low-density urban fabric (S.L. < 10%) – 11240", „Agricultural + Semi-natural areas + Wetlands – 20000" and "Forests – 30000" together.

According to this classification, we selected 20 random sampling points in each habitat type with at least 100 m distance between sampling points and the suitability of 50 m radius buffer zone of the points for our surveys and experiments, i.e. the existence of shrubs and no buildings within this zones. All of the surveys and experiments detailed below were conducted at the same sampling points and the same time in 2013: once in May (the middle of the breeding season of birds) and repeated one month later in June (the end of the breeding season), thereby excluding the possible impact of passage migrant birds or post-breeding movements.

2.2. Bird survey

Bird species and the number of individuals were recorded at selected sampling points (n = 20 survey points per habitat type) with fixed-radius point count method (Bibby et al., 2000). A single point count comprised a 10-min watch (using 12 × 50 binoculars) during which all birds were recorded by sight or sound within 50 m around the sampling point. Censuses were carried out twice, in May and June, under good weather conditions (no rain, little wind) from sunrise until 10 a.m. Simultaneous point counts were conducted by three ornithologists in the three habitat types. The three bird recorders rotated their habitat survey position between the two survey rounds (the urban observer moved to suburban in the second round, etc.) in order to reduce potential bias caused by the individual recorder. Bird abundance was calculated by taking the highest abundance value for each bird species at each survey point (Bibby et al., 2000).

2.3. Artificial nest experiment

We exposed one artificial shrub nest at every sampling point (n = 20 nests per habitat type), made by forming cup shapes (12 cm in diameter and 8 cm in deep) from fine wire mesh, weaving the baskets with raffia dyed in brown. We studied nest predation of shrub nests only since ground-nesting birds are less common in urban areas (Chamberlain et al., 2009). Nest baskets were affixed to vegetation using wires and were lined with leaf litter and dry grass collected *in situ* (Kurucz et al.,

2012) (Photo B1 in Supplemental Material). The height of shrub nest locations was 154 ± 2 cm (mean \pm SEM) on different kind of deciduous and evergreen shrubs. Each artificial nest contained one commercial quail (*Coturnix coturnix*) and one natural colour plasticine (produced by KOH–I-NOOR, Czech Republic) egg of similar size, which was aerated at least for a week before the start of the experiment (Kurucz et al., 2012). We monitored nests 3, 6, 9, 12 and 16 days after their initial placement, at the same time, in the morning. We considered the nest to be predated only if the quail egg was damaged or missing (Purger et al., 2012). Plasticine eggs were used for the identification of nest predators, as plasticine preserves tooth and beak imprints left behind by predators (Purger et al., 2012). Based on these marks, usually four categories (guilds) of egg predators can be distinguished. Large birds: large triangular bill marks, most probably the Eurasian jay (*Garrulus glandarius*), small birds: small triangular bill marks, probably great tit (*Parus major*), large mammals: canine marks, probably mustelids (*Mustelidae*) or red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) and small mammals: incisor marks, such as marks left by rodents (Photo B2).

2.4. Arthropod survey

We placed one yellow double-sided sticky trap (10 × 10 cm, produced by Biocont Magyarország Kft, Hungary; Photo B3) on vegetation at every sampling point (n = 20 traps per habitat type) in dry and windless weather conditions. We used wires to hang them up at a similar height as artificial nests (approximately 1.5 m height above the ground), but not on the same plants. After three days the sticky traps were collected, covered by a plastic sheet, transported to the laboratory and stored in the fridge. We recorded the number of arthropods collected on both sides of the trap cards and using stereomicroscope identifying them at order level as it was difficult to identify to genus or even species because of the bad condition of individuals.

2.5. Dummy caterpillar experiment

Dummy caterpillars (3.5 mm diameter and 25 mm length) were made of green modelling clay (Fimo Soft by Staedtler, Germany; colour code: 50), and were glued using a contact glue (Jewellery glue by Rayher, Germany) to leaves of deciduous shrubs (Barber, 2012). We put four caterpillars at every sampling points (n = 80 caterpillars per habitat type), on the same plants where artificial nests were, although at a distance of 1–1.5 m from the nests and each other. Caterpillars were exposed for 24 h, whereupon we recorded the presence/absence of predation, i.e. marks left on dummy caterpillars by birds (Photo B4).

2.6. Data analysis

All statistical tests were performed with R 3.4.4 software (R Development Core Team, 2018). Effect of urbanization on bird species richness and abundance was analysed using linear regression models. In order to test the effect of urbanization on the community composition of birds, we additionally performed redundancy analyses (RDA). Prior to this analysis, the species matrix was transformed with the Hellinger-transformation (Legendre and Gallagher, 2001). This transformation allows the use of Euclidean-based ordination methods with community composition data containing many zeros. Pseudo-F values with the corresponding P values were calculated by permutation tests based on 999 permutations. Calculations were performed using the 'vegan' package for R (Oksanen et al., 2016).

We analysed the effect of urbanization on the daily probability of nest survival using a generalised linear mixed-effects model (glmm) with binomial error distribution, logit link function, where nest fate was the denominator (0 = survived, 1 = predated) and nest days was the numerator. This method is known as Mayfield logistic regression (Hazler, 2004). Nest days were rounded up to the nearest day since the binomial model can work with integers only (Hazler, 2004). Additionally, the month was included in the model as a random factor. The calculation was performed using the 'lme4' package for R (Bates et al., 2014).

To compare prey abundance (number of insects collected on sticky traps) between habitats, we used general linear mixed-effects model (lme) implemented in the 'nlme' package for R (Pinheiro et al., 2014). The month was included in the model as a random factor. Finally, caterpillar predation data were analysed also using a glmm with binomial errors, logit link function, involving predation event as the denominator. Before the analysis, data were pooled per sampling points in a way that we had presence/absence of predation event per sampling point. The month was also included in this model as a random factor. Calculations were performed using the 'lme4' package for R (Bates et al., 2014).

We examined spatial autocorrelation in the residuals of the applied models using Moran's I statistic, calculated with the 'spdep' package for R (Bivand and Wong, 2018). Based on the test, our models partially showed significant spatial autocorrelation (see Appendix A in Supplemental Material), that we had to account in the analyses. Hence, we applied autocovariate regression models, by adding a distance-weighted function of neighbouring response values to the basic lm and glmm models, based on the geographic coordinates of the sampling points (Dormann et al., 2007).

3. Results

3.1. Bird communities

A total of 34 bird species were recorded (Table 1). The most abundant species were the European Blackbird (*Turdus merula*, n = 121 individuals) followed by the Common Swift (*Apus apus*, n = 92), Great Tit (*Parus major*, n = 51), House Sparrow (*Passer*

Table 1

List of bird species and their abundances (total number) recorded in the study region (the city of Pécs, Baranya county, Hungary) along an urbanization gradient (urban, suburban, and rural habitats). Bird diet preferences (Dip) according to the type of prey: G-generalist, C-carnivorous, sm-small mammals, i-insectivorous, (c)-caterpillars, g-granivorous, f-frugivorous. Nest site preferences (Nsp): gr-ground, b-buildings, s-shrubs, t-trees, (h) holes, bp-brood parasites. *Species were categorized according to Cramp et al., 1977–1994.

Scientific name	English name	Dip*	Nsp*	Urban	Suburban	Rural
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i>	Long-tailed Tit	i(c)/g	s	0	0	1
<i>Apus apus</i>	Common Swift	i(c)	b	58	34	0
<i>Buteo buteo</i>	Common Buzzard	C(sm)	t	0	0	1
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i>	European Goldfinch	g/i(c)	t	6	4	0
<i>Carduelis chloris</i>	European Greenfinch	g/i(c)	t	9	8	1
<i>Coccothrauste coccothraustes</i>	Hawfinch	g/i(c)	t	0	0	2
<i>Columba livia f. domestica</i>	Domestic Pigeon	g	b	38	2	0
<i>Columba palumbus</i>	Common Wood Pigeon	g	s/t	21	10	8
<i>Corvus frugilegus</i>	Rook	G	t	0	9	12
<i>Cuculus canorus</i>	Common Cuckoo	i(c)	bp	0	0	3
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	Eurasian Blue Tit	i(c)/g	b/t(h)	3	0	0
<i>Dendrocopos major</i>	Great Spotted Woodpecker	i/g	t(h)	1	0	1
<i>Emberiza citrinella</i>	Yellowhammer	g/i	gr	0	0	2
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	European Robin	i(c)/g	gr/t(h)	2	0	1
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>	Common Chaffinch	g/i(c)	s/t	18	5	5
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i>	Eurasian Jay	G(c)	s/t	0	1	2
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn Swallow	i	b	0	2	0
<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i>	Common Nightingale	i	gr/s	0	3	4
<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>	Eurasian Golden Oriole	i/f	t	0	2	7
<i>Parus ater</i>	Coal Tit	i(c)/g/f	s/t(h)	0	1	0
<i>Parus major</i>	Great Tit	i(c)/g	b/t(h)	22	15	14
<i>Parus palustris</i>	Marsh Tit	i(c)/g	t(h)	0	0	1
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House Sparrow	i/g	b/t	26	17	5
<i>Passer montanus</i>	Eurasian Tree Sparrow	i(c)/g	b/t(h)	1	0	0
<i>Phasianus colchicus</i>	Common Pheasant	G	gr	0	1	3
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>	Black Redstart	i/g/f	b	2	3	0
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	Common Chiffchaff	i(c)	gr	0	0	2
<i>Serinus serinus</i>	European Serin	g	s/t	9	2	0
<i>Sitta europaea</i>	Wood Nuthatch	i(c)/g	t(h)	1	0	2
<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Eurasian Collared Dove	g	b,s,t	19	15	9
<i>Streptopelia turtur</i>	European Turtle Dove	g	s/t	0	3	0
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>	Eurasian Blackcap	i/f	s	0	4	4
<i>Turdus merula</i>	European Blackbird	i(c)/g/f	b/s/t	53	49	19
<i>Turdus philomelos</i>	Song Thrush	i(c)/f	s/t	0	2	4

domesticus, $n = 48$), Eurasian Collared Dove (*Streptopelia decaocto*, $n = 43$), Domestic Pigeons (*Columba livia f. domestica*, $n = 40$), and Wood Pigeon (*Columba palumbus*, $n = 39$) (Fig. 1). Based on our analyses, the bird species richness did not change significantly along the urbanization gradient, although the highest richness was measured in urban and the lowest in rural areas (Table 2; Fig. 2a). However, bird abundance increased significantly with increasing urbanization. Significantly more individuals were observed in urban than in suburban or rural areas. Although the number of observed individuals was higher in suburban areas than in the rural ones, this difference was not significant (Table 2; Fig. 2b). The analyses indicated similar patterns when considering only “shrub nester” or only “insectivorous” species (Table 2).

Habitat type had a significant effect on bird community composition, namely, different bird species occurred along the urbanization gradient (11.4%, pseudo- $F_{2,57} = 2.67$, $P = 0.001$). The first RDA axis divided urban habitats from the other two, whereas the second RDA axis further subdivided the bird communities by separating suburban both from rural and urban habitats (Fig. 3). Urban habitats were characterised by typical synanthropic species, such as the Domestic Pigeon, House Sparrow, and Common Swift, as well by Common Chaffinch (*Fringilla coelebs*) and European Serin (*Serinus serinus*). In suburban habitats, there were species with high abundances, included the European Blackbird, Eurasian Collared Dove, Common Swift, and Great Tit, although these species often occurred in urban habitats as well. Species characteristic of the suburban habitats included the Eurasian Blackcap (*Sylvia atricapilla*), Common Nightingale (*Luscinia megarhynchos*), and Eurasian Jay (*Garrulus glandarius*). These species were represented by very few individuals and were often observed in rural habitats as well. Finally, the rural bird communities had typical woodland species, such as the Eurasian Golden Oriole (*Oriolus oriolus*), Common Cuckoo (*Cuculus canorus*), Song Thrush (*Turdus philomelos*), or the Common Pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*) (Fig. 3), that usually inhabit farmlands, scrubs and near-natural habitats around settlements.

3.2. Nest predation

Overall, 24% of 120 artificial nests were attacked during the study period (29 predation events), with similar predation rates in May and June. The highest predation rate was observed in the rural habitats (48% of nests, $n = 19/40$), whereas similarly low predation rates were detected in urban (13%, $n = 5/40$) and suburban habitats (13%, $n = 5/40$). This was also

Fig. 1. Relative abundances of the 34 detected bird species in urban, suburban, and rural habitats, calculated as the sum number of individuals (counted at the 20 sampling points) of the given species per the total number of birds in the defined habitat. For the full scientific and English species names see [Table 1](#).

Table 2

Effects of urbanization (U: urban, S: suburban, R: rural) on bird species richness and abundance, arthropods, daily nest survival rates of artificial shrub nests and predation of dummy caterpillars along the different habitat types. The contrast between suburban and urban habitats was derived by re-fitting the models using urban habitat as the baseline level. SEM: standard error of mean, P: value of significance, *for references see [Table 1](#).

	Comparison	Estimate ± SEM	P
Bird richness (total)	U – S	−0.88 ± 0.64	0.172
	S – R	0.12 ± 0.65	0.857
	U – R	1.00 ± 0.62	0.111
Bird richness (shrub nesters only*)	U – S	−0.15 ± 0.44	0.729
	S – R	0.32 ± 0.45	0.488
	U – R	0.47 ± 0.43	0.277
Bird richness (insectivorous only*)	U – S	−0.32 ± 0.53	0.549
	S – R	0.38 ± 0.55	0.495
	U – R	0.05 ± 0.52	0.918
Bird abundance (total)	U – S	−5.05 ± 2.02	0.015
	S – R	3.44 ± 2.06	0.102
	U – R	8.49 ± 1.95	<0.001
Bird abundance (shrub nesters only)	U – S	−1.12 ± 1.27	0.381
	S – R	1.95 ± 1.29	0.139
	U – R	3.06 ± 1.22	0.015
Bird abundance (insectivorous only)	U – S	−2.44 ± 1.54	0.117
	S – R	3.29 ± 1.57	0.041
	U – R	5.73 ± 1.49	<0.001
Arthropod abundance	U – S	3.05 ± 7.90	0.700
	S – R	6.44 ± 8.09	0.428
	U – R	3.39 ± 7.65	0.658
Daily nest survival rate	U – S	−0.03 ± 0.64	0.957
	S – R	−1.49 ± 0.52	0.004
	U – R	−1.46 ± 0.52	0.005
Caterpillar predation	U – S	1.44 ± 0.59	0.016
	S – R	0.90 ± 0.56	0.106
	U – R	−0.53 ± 0.63	0.397

Fig. 2. Mean (\pm SEM) species richness (a) and abundance (b) of birds per urban, suburban, and rural habitats.

reflected in the analysis of the Mayfield nest survival rates since we found significantly lower daily nest survival rates in rural habitats compared to suburban and urban ones (Table 2; Fig. 4).

Quail eggs were removed from nest by the predators in 10 cases out of the total 29 predation events, and we found broken eggshells in 19 nests. On plasticine eggs (that we used for the identification of predators) we found beak marks by small-bodied birds in 10 cases, whereas 12 plasticine eggs disappeared from the nests. In 7 cases, plasticine eggs remained intact, so we could not identify the predator responsible.

3.3. Potential food resources

Altogether, 5100 flying arthropods were captured (mean number of arthropods/trap = 51.6 with min-max/trap = 0–176) during the study, mainly Diptera, Hemiptera and Hymenoptera, while Orthoptera and Coleoptera were less abundant (Table C1 in Supplemental Material). Total arthropod abundance was similar across all habitats (mean \pm SEM in urban habitats: 46.18 ± 4.8 , suburban habitats: 40.83 ± 6.5 and rural habitats: 40.50 ± 5.3) (Table 2). Due to the high number of unidentifiable individuals ($n = 709$), we did not analyse abundance data at the order level.

Out of 160 dummy caterpillars per habitat type, signs of birds' attack were found on 9 (5.6%) in the urban habitats, on 25 of them (15.6%) in the suburban habitats and 17 of them (10.6%) in the rural habitats. Despite the fact, that caterpillars in suburban habitats suffered higher predation rate than those in urban or rural habitats, a statistically significant difference was detected only between urban and suburban habitats (Table 2).

4. Discussion

Based on our results, a high level of urbanization may increase bird densities, but simplifies the communities. Although cities can provide additional and safer-than-rural nesting sites, the availability and consumption of food were independent of the level of urbanization. In our study, we found no significant effect of urbanization on bird species richness. However, bird abundance increased significantly with increasing urbanization. These results may suggest that high-level urbanization can increase densities of birds, whereas these communities are dominated by synanthropic species. These species are able to thrive in a wide variety of environmental conditions and can make use of a variety of different resources, therefore could adapt easier to the human-modified and built-in environment, and usually benefit from the potential of cities. Even though most urban studies have been done in the temperate climates, similar increased bird density was found along an urbanization gradient in tropical India for example (Kale et al., 2018). The overall abundance and biomass of birds often increase from rural to urban settings, with just a few species contributing to the majority of individuals (Blair, 2004; Chase and Walsh, 2006). Thus, researchers have commonly observed lower species richness in urban habitats relative to that of the surrounding rural landscape (e.g. Cam et al., 2000). Our results are contrary to the conclusions of Clergeau et al. (2006), which showed that in European cities the total number of bird species generally decreased from periurban, and suburban sectors to city centres. Furthermore, many other studies that investigated the change in bird species richness across the full rural to urban gradient found that species richness often follows a hump-shaped curve with intermediate levels of urbanization exhibiting the highest species richness (e.g. Jokimäki and Suhonen, 1993; Tratalos et al., 2007). Presumably, suburban habitats by providing more varied environmental conditions and more diverse microhabitats might be even richer than more natural habitats. Sandström et al. (2006) pointed out the importance of vegetation structure in this aspect and described a positive correlation between shrub layer richness and the number of bird species. Although, in the present study we did not measure the vegetation cover around the sampling points, neither the visibility of the artificial shrub nests, according to the habitat categorization we used, in our study sites the proportion of green area in the urban habitats was low, but these green areas contained many bushes with thick foliage, providing shelter for nests and food for nestlings. Additionally, human-provided food and water sources (e.g. fountains) might be attractive for birds, as well as the structure of city-centre buildings, which can serve as nesting sites. This may explain the increasing diversity and densities of birds along the urbanization gradient in our study. A recent meta-analysis of urbanization effects on birds showed opposing general trends between bird species richness and abundance (Batáry et al., 2018). Species richness decreased from natural to urban areas, with a stronger decrease

Fig. 3. RDA ordination diagram with bird species (black points) and habitat types (open circles). For visibility, only bird species with the highest fraction of variance fitted by the two first factorial axes are indicated (Apuapu: *Apus apus*; Carcar: *Carduelis carduelis*; Colliv: *Columba livia f. domestica*; Corfru: *Corvus frugilegus*; Cuccan: *Cuculus canorus*; Fricoe: *Fringilla coelebs*; Lusmeg: *Luscinia megarhynchos*; Oriori: *Oriolus oriolus*; Parmaj: *Parus major*; Pasdom: *Passer domesticus*; Serser: *Serinus serinus*; Strdec: *Streptopelia decaocto*; Sylatr: *Sylvia atricapilla*; Turmer: *Turdus merula*). For English names see Table 1.

Fig. 4. Daily survival rates (\pm SEM) of artificial nests placed in urban, suburban, and rural habitats.

at the urban-suburban interface, whereas bird abundance showed a clear intermediate peak along the urban-rural gradient, although abundance in natural areas was comparable to that in suburban areas (Batáry et al., 2018). Our results could not support those conclusions, which suggest that urbanization exerts a consistent more-or-less negative linear effect on bird species richness and non-linear responses for abundance (Batáry et al., 2018).

Birds can be classified into urban-adapted or urban-sensitive categories based on their responses to urbanization (e.g. Gering and Blair, 1999). However, it is difficult to make generalization because ecological traits and local factors play a significant role in species responses to the altered environment, and also influence whether a species can adapt or cope with these environmental challenges (Luck and Smallbone, 2010). Noticeably, omnivorous and seed eating species are the most common in cities, that have adapted to using urban food resources and able to find favourable wintering sites because of intensive winter feeding by humans. Birds that feed on insects are more vulnerable to the negative effects of urbanization since they depend on the abundance and activity of the invertebrates they feed on (Clergeau et al., 1998; Jokimäki et al., 2002). In our study, the bird communities of the most urbanized areas were also dominated by generalist species, such as the

Blackbird, Domestic Pigeon or species that nest on buildings such as Common Swift. Based on a global analysis on the impacts of urbanization on bird diversity, Aronson et al. (2014) found that the majority of urban bird species are native in the world's cities and only a few cosmopolitan species occur across cities, that are considered as invasive species in many areas, such as Domestic Pigeon, House Sparrow and Common Starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*) (Møller et al., 2015; Morelli et al., 2016).

According to our artificial shrub nest experiment, urban and also suburban areas seem to be safer in terms of nesting than rural areas. Similar patterns, i.e. decrease in predation frequency from natural sites to urban sites were observed in previous studies performed in the same city (Bocz et al., 2017; Kurucz et al., 2012) and also by Gering and Blair (1999) in an American small town. Fischer et al. (2012) also showed in their review that the survival rates of songbirds typically increase with urbanization. From another point of view, the overall number of mesopredators tend to increase with urbanization, while the predation pressure on urban bird populations tend to decrease giving credence to the predation paradox (Fischer et al., 2012). A meta-analysis on predation rates in rural vs. urban areas presented strong evidence for reduced predation in urban settings but this analysis did not include corresponding data on predator communities (Eötvös et al., 2018). Another meta-analysis did not detect any strong relationship between urbanization and nest mortality, since the chance of natural nests to fail tended to decrease with increasing urbanization, supporting the “urban habitats as predation-safe zones” and “urban nest predator paradox” hypotheses, but survival rates of artificial nests tended to decrease with the level of urbanization, with higher predation in more urbanized study sites (Vincze et al., 2017). Predation is one of the fundamental mechanisms that structure natural communities (Shochat et al., 2006), thus the assemblage structure of nest predators could be one of the primary forces shaping urban bird communities, affecting the selection of their habitats and nesting sites, and thereby the development of their populations' space-time dynamics (Söderström et al., 1998; Weatherhead and Blouin-Demers, 2004). However, the breeding success of birds depends on how dispersed are green patches that are suitable for nesting sites, and how birds are sensitive to human presence at all (Jokimäki et al., 2020; Mikula et al., 2014). Behavioural responses to urbanization are species-specific and highly variable, thus predation pressure, however, may change with urbanization because the predator communities are thought to be different in urban environments compared to natural environments. In our study, we did not assess predator abundances, and the few predation events in urban and suburban habitats together with difficulties of predator identification hindered us in concluding about this paradox. However, the shrub nests are often depredated by birds (Weidinger, 2009), mainly by corvids (Madden et al., 2015), which usually take the eggs one by one from the nests (Vigallon and Marzluff, 2005). Our earlier research showed that Eurasian Jays (*Garrulus glandarius*) and tits (*Parus* spp.) were responsible for nest predation on shrub nests in the city of Pécs and surrounding areas (Purger et al., 2004; Kurucz et al., 2010). During the present bird survey, we observed Jays and Rooks (*Corvus frugilegus*) as well, mainly in the rural and suburban areas, so they may be responsible for the disappearance of many eggs. However, on the plasticine eggs, we recognized bill marks of small-bodied birds only, and did not find any sign of corvids. At the same time, Beech Martens (*Martes foina*) as potential large-bodied mammalian predator were frequently observed in many parts of the city, but in the absence of imprints on dummy eggs, there is no evidence of this either. A growing number of studies report that urban habitats support more diverse and/or abundant communities of generalist predators than do rural or wild landscapes, and that the dominant predators change along the rural-to-urban landscape gradient (e.g. Chace and Walsh, 2006; Jokimäki and Huhta, 2000; Jokimäki et al., 2005; Rodewald and Kearns, 2011; Sorace and Gustin, 2009). However, predators whose numbers increase in urban habitats are not necessarily important actual predators of birds or their nests in urban habitats (Rodewald and Kearns, 2011). The rich anthropogenic food resources of urban habitats make it likely that abundant predators shift their foraging behaviour in ways that might reduce their predation pressure on breeding birds (Rodewald et al., 2011; Weidinger, 2009). Besides, the response of individual predator species to urbanization varies greatly, influenced by a variety of factors such as dietary breadth, behavioural adaptability, habitat requirements and interspecific interactions among carnivores and with humans (Ordenana et al., 2010).

Food supply is widely accepted as the primary ultimate determinant of reproductive phenology in birds. For many bird species, arthropods are an important part of the diet, therefore the availability of arthropods might play an important role in modulating avian communities (Deviche and Davies, 2014). However, the response of arthropod abundance to urbanization varies widely among studies (Faeth et al., 2005), some of them reporting an increase in arthropod abundance along the urbanization gradient (Dreistadt et al., 1990; McIntyre et al., 2001), whereas others found a decrease or no effect (e.g. Croci et al., 2008; Hafernick and Reinhard, 1995). Discernibly, arthropods' responses to urbanization are often taxon-specific, highly variable, and linked to properties of urbanization that weaken top-down and/or bottom-up processes (Raupp et al., 2010). In our study, however, without focusing on any particular taxon, the potential food resources for birds (abundance of arthropods) did not correlate with the degree of urbanization, which suggests that it is not necessarily a key driver in habitat selection of birds within an urbanization gradient. Although, food consumption (predation pressure on dummy caterpillars by birds) was higher in suburban areas compared to urban and rural areas. This is partly in contrast with the findings of Ferrante et al. (2014), who showed higher caterpillar survival both in urban and suburban habitats than in forests. Although, in their dummy caterpillar study, they applied different arrangement (dummy caterpillars were fixed on the ground and not on the leaves), and did not consider bird attacks alone. Moreover, most of the bird species that we observed in the city centre do not feed on insects in general and do not prey on dummy caterpillars either. In consequence, the caterpillar predation rate should not correlate with bird densities in this context. Nevertheless, in Europe, human-provided food (private feeders and discarded organic waste) potentially provide a predictable, energy-rich resource that may increase food intake (Deviche and Davies, 2014). Thereby larger quantities of food available to birds in urban relative to neighbouring non-urban areas may play a role in the advanced reproductive phenology of urban birds (Chamberlain et al., 2009). Although, it remains unclear whether

and how the effect of human-provided food on avian reproductive phenology interacts with changes in natural food abundance and composition associated with urbanization.

5. Conclusion

Urban environments cannot be viewed as lost habitat for wildlife, but rather as new habitat with proper management having the potential to support diverse bird communities. However, the protection of bird diversity in urban habitats requires a thorough knowledge about their breeding opportunities, especially about the available nesting sites and food resources, as well as how predation pressure or predator assemblages affect bird communities in urbanized landscapes. In the present study, no consistent negative or positive urbanization effect could be detected, but it seems that both bird richness and densities increased moderately with urbanization, while these communities are dominated by some generalist and typical synanthropic species. Our results suggest that nesting in urban habitats may be safer at least for open cup shrub nesters, probably due to lower predation pressure and/or much favourable nesting sites provided by cities. Nevertheless, the food availability per se cannot be a key driver in habitat selection of birds within an urbanization gradient. In conclusion, future research should assess the effect of natural and human-provided food availability parallel, as well as the differences in survival chance and dispersion patterns between urban and non-urban populations. In light of our results, it is recommended that for a comprehensive study, the combined use of several sampling methods is needed in order to gain a more holistic picture of urbanization effects on birds. Since urbanization is not a purely physical process that affects biodiversity, socio-economic patterns such as urban structure, human population density, neighbourhood image, or household income should be also taken into account when studying urban ecosystems (Chamberlain et al., 2020).

Author contributions

K.K., J.J.P. and P.B. conceived the ideas and designed this study. K.K. and J.J.P. collected data. P.B. prepared the analyses. P.B. and K.K. interpreted the results and visualization. K.K. wrote the manuscript. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal relationship that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Appendices A (models used for statistical analyses), **B** (Photos of artificial nest, plasticine eggs with marks from predators, yellow sticky trap and dummy caterpillar with marks from a bird) and **C** (table showing the abundance of arthropod orders by urbanisation category) are available online.

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